

Heritage Data Governance in Regeneration: Lessons from England's High Street Heritage Action Zones

Abstract

Heritage data management has become increasingly critical as regeneration initiatives generate vast quantities of digital information, yet approaches to systematic data governance remain inconsistent across the sector. This paper examines heritage data practices within Historic England's High Street Heritage Action Zone (High Street HAZ) programme, focusing on case studies from Northallerton, Kirkham, and Chester. Through semi-structured interviews, questionnaires, and data audits conducted between 2021-2024, this research investigates how heritage datasets are created, shared, and preserved within planning processes, community wellbeing initiatives, and heritage research projects. Key findings reveal widespread but specific data reuse across all programme strands, alarmingly low awareness of Data Management Plans (DMPs), and fragmented approaches to data sharing and preservation. The study uncovers significant disparities between above-ground and below-ground archaeological data management, with the former lacking systematic archival requirements despite comparable heritage value. Commercial intellectual property practices often conflict with public access principles, whilst community-generated datasets face particular vulnerability without institutional support. The research demonstrates that easily accessible datasets are routinely reused whilst those requiring specialist access remain underutilised, highlighting the critical importance of data discoverability. The paper advocates for mandatory DMPs, hybrid governance models balancing local autonomy with national oversight, and clear intellectual property frameworks ensuring public benefit from publicly funded research. These findings contribute to emerging debates on digital heritage governance, offering evidence-based recommendations for improving data stewardship in heritage-led regeneration initiatives.

Keywords: Heritage data management, Digital governance, Urban regeneration, Planning policy, Community archives, Data stewardship

Introduction

The traditional high street faces unprecedented challenges in the twenty-first century, with decline accelerated by online retail, economic pressures, and the COVID-19 pandemic (Carmona, 2015; Lloyd-James *et al.*, 2020). In response, the UK government has implemented various initiatives to revitalise these crucial community spaces, recognising their importance beyond mere commercial function as places to meet, live, and work (Turley, 2019). The High Street Heritage Action Zone (High Street HAZ) programme, funded by £95 million from the UK government and led by Historic England, represents one of the most ambitious attempts to harness heritage as a catalyst for regeneration across 67 English high streets (Historic England, 2025).

This initiative combines investment in physical conservation with community engagement and cultural programming, aiming to foster civic pride, strengthen social cohesion, and stimulate economic growth (Historic England, 2025). However, whilst considerable attention has focused on the programme's tangible outcomes: restored shopfronts, repurposed buildings, and enhanced public realm, the digital legacy of these interventions remains underexplored. The High Street HAZ generated substantial volumes of heritage data, from planning documents and architectural surveys to oral histories and community-created digital content, yet the governance of these datasets has received limited critical examination.

Heritage data governance has emerged as a critical concern within digital heritage scholarship, reflecting broader debates about data stewardship, public access, and long-term preservation (Dallas, 2016; Huggett, 2020). The concept encompasses not merely technical considerations of storage and format, but the human elements of institutional and political processes through which heritage information is created, validated, shared, and sustained (Bowker, 2013; Gray *et al.*, 2018). As heritage practice becomes increasingly data-dependent, understanding these governance

dynamics becomes essential for ensuring that digital outputs serve both immediate project goals and broader public benefit.

Theoretical Framework and Regulatory Context

Within the UK heritage sector, data governance operates within a complex regulatory framework that shapes institutional responsibilities and professional practices. The Planning (Listed Buildings and Conservation Areas) Act 1990 establishes statutory duties for heritage protection, whilst the Historic Environment Records (HER) provide the primary information infrastructure for local heritage knowledge (Historic England, 2023). However, these frameworks evolved primarily around physical heritage protection rather than digital data stewardship, creating systematic gaps in governance arrangements.

The emergence of FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) within research contexts has provided frameworks for evaluating data quality (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016), whilst CARE principles (Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, Ethics) have offered ethical guidance for community-generated content (Carroll *et al.*, 2020). Archaeological data management has achieved relative systematisation through the OASIS (Online Access to the Index of archaeological investigations) framework, mandating deposition with the Archaeology Data Service for publicly funded investigations. However, equivalent requirements do not exist for above-ground heritage documentation, creating systematic disparities in preservation outcomes despite comparable heritage significance.

The intersection of heritage and planning presents particular challenges for data governance. Planning processes generate substantial documentary records through statutory requirements, yet these materials often remain siloed within local authority systems with limited integration into broader heritage infrastructures (Patrick, 2021). Community engagement activities produce valuable cultural documentation, but lack established preservation pathways (Flinn, 2007; Caswell & Cifor, 2016). Commercial consultants create technically sophisticated datasets, but often retain intellectual property rights that limit public access despite public funding (Jeffrey, 2015).

Recent scholarship has highlighted significant challenges in heritage data management, particularly around issues of accessibility, interoperability, and long-term preservation (Richards, 2017; Kansa & Kansa, 2018). However, the application of these frameworks within regeneration contexts remains limited, with most heritage data governance research focusing on museums, archives, or academic projects rather than planning-led interventions.

The High Street HAZ programme offers a unique lens for examining heritage data governance due to its scale, diversity, and hybrid governance structure. Operating through partnerships between Historic England, local authorities, commercial consultants, and community organisations, the initiative generated datasets across multiple domains: planning and conservation, community wellbeing, and heritage research. This multi-stakeholder environment created natural experiments in data management, revealing how different institutional cultures, professional norms, and community priorities shape the lifecycle of heritage information.

This paper addresses these gaps through detailed examination of heritage data practices within three High Street HAZ case studies: Northallerton (North Yorkshire), focusing on digital innovation and community archiving; Kirkham (Lancashire), emphasising heritage-based social prescribing and wellbeing; and Chester (Cheshire), centring on built heritage conservation within a nationally significant historic environment. These sites were selected to represent different geographical contexts, project emphases, and governance arrangements, enabling comparative analysis of how local capacity, institutional partnerships, and community priorities shape data outcomes.

The research contributes to several scholarly conversations. Within heritage studies, it extends critical analysis of digital governance beyond traditional cultural institutions into planning and regeneration contexts (Smith, 2006; Harrison, 2013). Within planning scholarship, it foregrounds the cultural and archival dimensions of development processes, areas often overlooked in policy analysis (Pendlebury, 2012). Within digital humanities and information science, it provides empirical evidence of how data governance operates within complex multi-stakeholder

environments, offering lessons for other interdisciplinary collaborative projects (Borgman, 2015).

The paper's central argument is that heritage data governance within regeneration contexts reflects broader tensions between short-term project delivery and long-term cultural stewardship, between local autonomy and national coordination, and between commercial interests and public access. These tensions are not merely technical or administrative but reflect deeper questions about who controls heritage knowledge, how cultural value is recognised and preserved, and what responsibilities accompany public investment in heritage research.

Materials and Methods

This research employed a mixed-methods approach combining qualitative and quantitative data collection techniques to examine heritage data practices across the High Street HAZ programme. The methodological framework was designed to capture both formal governance structures and informal practices that shape heritage data management in practice.

Methodological Justification

The complexity of heritage data governance within regeneration contexts necessitated a multi-faceted research approach capable of examining both institutional frameworks and lived practice. Semi-structured interviews provided depth and nuance in understanding how different stakeholders navigate data management challenges, revealing informal practices and institutional cultures that shape outcomes beyond formal policies. Questionnaires enabled systematic comparison across stakeholder groups and geographic contexts, identifying patterns that might not emerge from qualitative data alone. Data audits provided objective assessment of actual preservation outcomes, enabling evaluation of gaps between stated intentions and achieved results.

This triangulation approach was essential because heritage data governance operates simultaneously at multiple levels: individual professional practice, institutional policy, and systemic regulatory frameworks. No single method could

adequately capture this complexity, whilst the combination enabled cross-validation of findings and identification of systematic patterns across different data sources.

The mixed-methods design also addressed the challenge of researching within professional networks where participants might be reluctant to discuss institutional failures or policy gaps in interview settings. The questionnaire provided anonymous reporting mechanisms, whilst data audits offered independent verification of preservation outcomes regardless of stakeholder perceptions or claims.

Case Study Selection

Three High Street HAZ locations were selected for detailed analysis: Northallerton, Kirkham, and Chester (Figure 1). These sites were chosen to represent different geographical regions (Yorkshire, Lancashire, and Cheshire respectively), varying scales of urban context (market town, small town, and historic city), and distinct project emphases (digital innovation, community wellbeing, and built heritage conservation). This purposive sampling strategy enabled examination of how local capacity, institutional partnerships, and community priorities shaped data governance outcomes across different contexts.

Figure 1, Map of the HSHAZ locations, with emphasis on the three case studies (author's own)

The selection was constrained to sites within England to maintain consistency with the High Street HAZ programme structure and Historic England's regulatory framework. Whilst this geographical limitation affects the generalisability of findings to other national contexts, it enables detailed analysis of how English heritage

governance frameworks operate in practice. The temporal scope focused primarily on the period 2020-2024, corresponding to the main High Street HAZ delivery phase, with supplementary data collection continuing through 2024 to assess post-project outcomes.

Semi-Structured Interviews

Semi-structured interviews formed the primary qualitative data collection method, conducted throughout the High Street HAZ programme period from 2021 to 2024. This longitudinal approach enabled examination of how data practices evolved during project delivery and provided insight into changing priorities and emerging challenges.

Interviewed participants were selected through purposive sampling to represent key stakeholder groups involved in heritage data creation, management, and use. These included Historic England staff (HAZ Project Officers responsible for coordinating multiple sites), local authority personnel (HAZ Project Leads managing individual locations, built environment officers, and conservation staff), heritage professionals (architects, consultants, and contractors), community group representatives, and cultural programme participants.

The interview guide was structured around four thematic areas derived from the research questions: data creation and reuse practices, sharing and accessibility arrangements, preservation and archiving approaches, and perceived value and legacy of heritage datasets (Appendix 1). Questions were designed to be open-ended, allowing participants to reflect on their experiences whilst ensuring consistent coverage of key topics across interviews.

Most interviews were conducted face-to-face at participants' workplaces or community venues to build rapport and enable discussion of specific datasets or platforms in situ. However, interviews with Historic England regional staff and some commercial consultants were conducted via video call due to geographical constraints. Interviews typically lasted 60-90 minutes and were audio-recorded with participants' consent.

Following established qualitative research protocols, the researcher engaged in reflexive practice throughout the data collection process (Rose, 1997; Sultana, 2007). As a researcher embedded within the heritage sector through collaborative doctoral partnership arrangements, particular attention was paid to potential conflicts of interest and the influence of professional networks on data access and interpretation. Regular supervision and peer discussion helped maintain analytical distance whilst leveraging insider knowledge to navigate technical and institutional complexities.

Questionnaire

A structured questionnaire was developed to capture systematic data on data management practices across the broader High Street HAZ programme (Appendix 2). The questionnaire employed predominantly closed-ended questions using seven-point Likert scales, supplemented by open-ended items to capture qualitative context (Finstad, 2010; Dawes, 2008). Seven-point scales were selected to maximise response variance whilst avoiding the complexity of ten-point alternatives that can reduce response quality in electronic surveys.

Five separate questionnaire versions were created to reflect different stakeholder roles and contexts: HAZ Project Officers, HAZ Project Leads, and architects/consultants for each of the three case study locations. This tailored approach ensured questions remained relevant to participants' specific experiences whilst maintaining consistency in core themes.

The questionnaire was implemented using Qualtrics survey software and distributed via email using personalised mail merge techniques to improve response rates. Distribution occurred at multiple timepoints throughout the High Street HAZ programme to capture changing practices and perceptions over time.

Limitations of Quantitative Analysis:

The modest response rate (n=29) necessitates careful interpretation of quantitative findings. Rather than claiming statistical representativeness, the questionnaire data is treated as indicative of trends within this specific professional network.

Percentages are presented to show patterns within the respondent group but cannot

be generalised to the broader heritage sector without further research. This limitation was anticipated given the specialised nature of the research population and time constraints within project environments. The questionnaire data primarily serves to triangulate qualitative findings and identify areas requiring further investigation rather than providing statistically robust conclusions.

Data Audits

Systematic data audits were conducted to examine the actual outputs and preservation outcomes of heritage data creation across the three case studies. These audits focused on publicly accessible repositories where High Street HAZ-related materials might reasonably be expected to appear: local authority planning portals, Historic Environment Records, the Archaeology Data Service, and project-specific websites or digital platforms.

For each case study, planning applications submitted during the High Street HAZ period (January 2020 to March 2024) within the designated high street conservation areas were identified and analysed. This yielded comprehensive datasets of planning-related documentation including heritage statements, design and access statements, photographs, architectural drawings, and supporting technical reports.

Each planning application was documented to identify data types present, file formats used, sources cited, and evidence of data reuse from previous applications or external sources. Particular attention was paid to the use of historical photographs, maps, and heritage research, as these materials often indicate connection to broader heritage datasets and archives.

Additional audits examined community-generated content through project websites, social media platforms, and cultural programme outputs. This proved more challenging due to the ephemeral nature of many digital platforms and the informal governance arrangements surrounding community data. Where materials had been removed or become inaccessible, this was noted as evidence of data vulnerability.

The data audit methodology was designed to assess not only what heritage data was created, but its discoverability, accessibility, and apparent integration with established heritage infrastructures. This approach enabled evaluation of the gap

between data creation and effective preservation, revealing patterns of systematic loss or marginalisation of heritage information.

Integration of Methods

The three methodological approaches were designed to complement each other in addressing the research questions. Interviews provided detailed understanding of stakeholder experiences and institutional cultures, revealing why certain practices developed and how governance challenges were navigated in practice. The questionnaire systematised these insights across a broader sample, identifying common patterns and quantifying the prevalence of specific practices. Data audits provided independent verification of outcomes, enabling assessment of whether stated intentions translated into effective preservation and accessibility.

This methodological triangulation was particularly important given the sensitive nature of institutional critique within professional networks. Interviewed participants might be reluctant to highlight failures in their own organisations, whilst questionnaire anonymity enabled more candid reporting of systemic challenges. Data audits provided objective evidence independent of stakeholder perceptions, enabling critical assessment of governance effectiveness regardless of individual claims or institutional representations.

Analytical Framework

Analysis employed an iterative approach combining deductive analysis based on established heritage data governance frameworks (particularly FAIR and CARE principles) with inductive identification of themes emerging from the empirical material (Charmaz, 2006). Initial analysis focused on identifying practices related to data creation, sharing, preservation, and governance across the three case studies.

Comparative analysis examined similarities and differences in approaches across sites, stakeholder groups, and project types. This revealed systematic patterns that transcended individual project characteristics, pointing to structural factors influencing heritage data governance. Cross-case synthesis enabled identification of both successful practices and systemic barriers that could inform recommendations for future programmes.

Throughout the analysis, attention was paid to power dynamics and institutional hierarchies that shaped data governance outcomes. The research recognised that data practices are not neutral technical choices but reflect broader patterns of authority, resource distribution, and professional culture within the heritage sector (Kitchin, 2014; Taylor, 2017).

Ethical Considerations

The research received ethical approval from the University of York and was conducted in accordance with Historic England's research ethics guidelines. All participants provided informed consent for interview participation and audio recording. Questionnaire responses were anonymised during collection and analysis.

Particular care was taken regarding community-generated data and informal archives, following principles of ethical engagement with community knowledge (Carroll *et al.*, 2020). Where participants requested anonymity or expressed concerns about institutional critique, these preferences were respected through appropriate data handling and reporting practices.

Results

The analysis reveals significant variations in heritage data management practices across the High Street HAZ programme, with outcomes shaped by institutional capacity, professional culture, and governance arrangements rather than technical constraints alone. The findings are organised around four key themes: data reuse patterns, creation practices, sharing mechanisms, and preservation outcomes.

Data Reuse Patterns and Accessibility

Data reuse was widespread across all High Street HAZ strands, but patterns of usage revealed significant barriers to accessing existing heritage information (Appendix 3). Within planning processes, statutory requirements drove consistent reuse of specific dataset types, particularly Historic England listing records (appearing in 30% of Northallerton and 20% of Chester applications), historical maps for map regression analysis (18% of Northallerton, 6% Kirkham and 24% of Chester applications), and previous planning decisions (27% of Northallerton and 6% of

Chester applications). However, this reuse was often superficial, with consultants copying and pasting text from statutory sources rather than engaging critically with heritage significance assessments.

The questionnaire data (Appendix 4, Table 1) revealed that 57% of HAZ Project Leads reported reusing existing datasets within their High Street HAZ work, with local repositories being the most frequently accessed resource (83.33%). Historic England datasets were widely used (66.67%), validating investment in national platforms such as the Heritage Gateway and National Heritage List for England. However, Historic Environment Records were significantly underutilised (41.67%) despite their statutory role as "the primary source of information about the historic environment of a local area" (Historic England, 2023).

Table 1: Location of Data Sources Used in High Street HAZ Projects (n=24)

Where was most of the data found?	Count	Percentage
Local archive	20	83.33%
Historic England	16	66.67%
Community Groups	15	62.50%
Planning portal	13	54.17%
Local HER	10	41.67%
County Records Office	9	37.50%
Archaeology Data Service	4	16.67%
Other	6	25.00%

A critical finding emerged regarding data accessibility and reuse likelihood. Materials stored in easily discoverable locations, particularly those indexed by search engines or available through familiar platforms, were consistently reused, whilst those requiring specialist access or institutional mediation remained largely unused. As one heritage professional noted during interviews:

"Archives don't form a big part of what we do... a passing moment or two of just quickly looking through what's available" (Andrew Haley, Paul Hogarth Company, personal communication, 24 August 2023).

This accessibility bias was particularly evident in Chester, where despite extensive Historic England research on the medieval Rows available through the Archaeology Data Service (Brown, 1999), planning applications showed minimal engagement with this resource. Instead, applicants relied on readily available materials such as photographs discoverable through search engines or basic historical maps from free online sources (Figures 2-4). The contrast between available scholarship and actual usage highlighted the critical importance of data discoverability and access mechanisms.

Fig. 2. Top left: The site of No. 43 - 47 Bridge Street, arrowed red. Hodkinson's building No. 31 - 35 Bridge Street, built 1863 is in the background. The photograph is probably late 1860's arrowed orange. Top right: The site of No. 43 - 47 Bridge Street, arrowed red. Lockwood's building No. 31 - 35 Bridge Street, St Michael's Row, arrowed orange and built 1909, is in the foreground.

Figure 2, above, Historical photograph used in planning application 23/02160/LBC (Cragg, 2023), and figures 3 and 4, below, the same photos found as part of this research (left) SMR1863.jpg, uploaded by Hooligan (2014), Chester ShoutWiki (CC BY-SA 3.0); (right) Vintage Lantern Slide (Photo no. 13935905), © The Keasbury-Gordon Photograph Archive / Mary Evans.).

Community engagement projects demonstrated different reuse patterns, with hands-on interaction with physical archival materials proving particularly valuable for wellbeing outcomes. In Kirkham, participants' engagement with the Kirkham in Amounderness Local History and Heritage collection at St Michael's Church enabled what project coordinators described as opportunities for people to be:

"Their own experts [which was] massive in terms of pride" (Sue Flowers, personal communication, 21 July 2023).

The tactile nature of original documents, maps, and photographs facilitated storytelling and memory-sharing in ways that digital alternatives could not replicate.

Facebook groups emerged as unexpected but significant heritage data repositories, particularly the "Kirkham & Wesham Memories of the Past" group, which provided access to otherwise private photographic collections. However, the reliance on commercial social media platforms for heritage data sharing raised questions about long-term accessibility and preservation, issues that became acute when project websites and social media accounts became inactive after funding ended.

Heritage Data Creation Practices

The High Street HAZ programme generated diverse datasets across multiple formats and contexts, but creation practices varied significantly depending on professional domain and regulatory framework. Planning-related data creation was extensive but highly standardised, with all applications (100%) containing PDF submission of core documents, supplemented by photographic evidence (74% of applications) and technical drawings (65% elevations and 63% plans of applications).

However, the predominance of PDF formats created significant challenges for long-term reusability. Whilst PDFs ensure document integrity and universal readability, they severely limit computational analysis and data extraction. Quality degradation was commonly observed during format conversion, with metadata loss, character corruption, and image compression compromising evidential value. In several instances, crucial information such as data source references was truncated or corrupted during PDF conversion (Figure 5), undermining the traceability of heritage evidence.

Supporting Document Covered In Another Document

Proposal Number:	PP-11644744
Version Number:	1
Document Type:	Photographs and photomontages
This document is covered in:	Design and access statement - R22017 heritage statement-1711
Document Description:	

Figure 5, Example of data loss during PDF conversion process. The error is the “This document is Covered in:” box where the text is truncated at the heritage statements number, meaning the link to the associated record is lost (Hodson, 2022).

Archaeological investigations demonstrated markedly different data creation practices. All below-ground archaeological work followed established workflows requiring registration through OASIS (Online Access to the Index of archaeological investigations) and deposition with the Archaeology Data Service. This systematic approach contrasted sharply with above-ground heritage documentation, which lacked comparable archival requirements despite often documenting equally irreplaceable historical fabric.

The disparity was particularly evident in Chester, where consultant-produced building condition surveys, architectural documentation, and heritage assessments were delivered as PDFs to planning portals without systematic integration into Historic Environment Records or national repositories. Even technically sophisticated output

such as 3D models (Figure 6) and drone photography remained in commercial custody despite their potential value for heritage management and public engagement, shared only as flat 2D images in PDF format.

Figure 6, a 3D model made for application 21-04050-LBC (Potts, 2021).

Community-generated data represented the most diverse and innovative category of heritage data creation. The Northallerton Heritage Hub exemplified best practice in this domain, systematically digitising community-contributed materials (Figure 7) and recording oral histories in uncompressed WAV format following British Library and Oral History Society guidelines, whilst establishing clear custodianship arrangements with the North Yorkshire County Records Office. As the project coordinator noted:

"From the outset, we have had in mind that the digital archive that we are creating through our work at the Hub would be a key legacy of the project" (Virginia Arrowsmith, personal communication, 10 March 2023).

Figure 7, 19th-century commercial bills relating to the George Inn, contributed by local business owner Suzie Valentine (credit Virginia Arrowsmith).

Conversely, Kirkham's wellbeing programme produced valuable community outputs, including collaborative maps (Figure 8), scrapbooks, and creative works, but lacked systematic digitisation or archival planning. The emphasis on physical, tactile interaction with heritage materials, whilst beneficial for immediate wellbeing outcomes, created vulnerability for long-term preservation without additional intervention.

Figure 8, Community-created heritage map from Kirkham wellbeing programme (author's own).

Data Management Planning and Awareness

The research revealed alarming gaps in systematic data management planning across the High Street HAZ programme. Questionnaire responses indicated that over 65% of participants were unfamiliar with Data Management Plans (DMPs), and amongst those who recognised the term, only 2 out of 28 had implemented DMPs within their High Street HAZ work (Table 2). This represented a significant departure from research sector norms, where DMPs are increasingly mandated by funding bodies.

Table 2: Awareness and Use of Data Management Plans (n=26)

		Did you use a DMP in the HSHAZ?	
		No	Yes
Have you heard of a DMP?	Maybe	3	-
	No	14	-
	Yes	9	2
	Total	26	2

Table 1, the number of stakeholders who knew of Data Management Plans and stakeholders that used Data Management Plans as part of the HSHAZ.

The absence of systematic data planning created cascading effects throughout project lifecycles. Without advance consideration of archival requirements, appropriate file formats, or preservation pathways, heritage data often defaulted to storage within the data creators' organisational servers. This created substantial variations in data quality and accessibility, even within single projects.

Storage arrangements reflected the ad hoc nature of data management planning. Most heritage data was stored on internal online drives (75%) or local council systems (17.86%), with limited consideration of long-term accessibility beyond immediate project needs, with only 20% of respondents depositing their data in formal repositories (Tables 3 and 4).

Storage Location	Count	Percentage
Team online drive (e.g. Google Drive/Dropbox)	21	75.00%
Council drives	5	17.86%
Personal Online Drive	1	3.57%

Table 3, above: Data Storage Locations During Projects (n=27). Table 4, below: Data Deposit Practices (n=25)

Did you deposit your data?

Yes	5
No	20

The questionnaire revealed widespread concern about data loss, with 56% of respondents agreeing that valuable datasets were being lost (Table 5). When datasets were perceived as being lost, participants identified the primary causes as absence of publication requirements (100%), archival requirements (93%), requirements for data to be archived (79%) and public access requirements (79%) (Table 6). These responses suggested that data governance failures reflected systemic policy gaps rather than individual oversight.

To what extent do you agree that valuable datasets are being lost? Count

Strongly agree	1
Agree	5
Somewhat agree	8
Neither agree nor disagree	10
Strongly disagree	1

Table 5, above: Perceptions of Data Loss (n=25). Table 6, below: Identified Causes of Data Loss (Multiple responses possible)

Reasons for Data Loss	Count
There is no requirement to publish data	14
There is no requirement to archive data	13
There is no requirement to make data publicly accessible	11
Data is not archived	11
Data is not published	7
Data is not made publicly accessible	6
Other	3

When data was deposited, respondents primarily used text-based file formats such as PDF and DOCX, supplemented by specialised formats including JPEG images, audio files, and paper copies (Table 7). The predominance of PDF format in both creation and archiving practices reflected professional norms prioritising document integrity over computational accessibility.

Table 7: File Formats Created and Archived

Format	Created	Archived
PDF	29	3
Word document (.doc/.docx)	27	3
JPEG	25	2
Excel (.xlsx)	22	0
Spreadsheet	16	0
Paper	15	2
PNG	9	2
Audio file (.mp3)	8	2
Audio file (.wav)	3	2

Format	Created	Archived
TIFF	2	0
Other	2	2

Further challenges in data management were evident in data sharing practices. Whilst formal outputs such as listings updates and photographic surveys followed established archival protocols, embedding these datasets within the broader programme proved problematic. As one Historic England team member observed:

"The sheer volume of High Street HAZ's... for just one listing team... [and Chester has] a large number of listed buildings within it... [that] gets uploaded at the end once DCMS has accepted it" (Jane Rimmer, Historic England, personal communication, 4 March 2024).

Community data sharing presented different but equally complex challenges. The Heritage Hub in Northallerton developed sophisticated approaches to balancing individual ownership with collective benefit, enabling contributors to retain legal ownership whilst facilitating systematic preservation through the County Records Office. Copyright complexities were acknowledged by project staff:

*"Copyright is a huge area, and I would say it's one of the biggest challenges for curators, archivists, heritage professionals... **recorded** speech is separate to sound. There's a lot of complexity in copyright" (Virginia Arrowsmith, personal communication, 2 September 2022).*

The absence of clear intellectual property frameworks created particular vulnerabilities for community-generated content. Without explicit licensing arrangements, materials contributed through social media platforms, community workshops, or informal documentation remained subject to platform terms of service and individual contributor preferences, limiting potential for systematic preservation or academic reuse.

Digital Preservation and Platform Precarity

The research revealed significant risks to long-term digital preservation arising from reliance on commercial platforms and short-term funding arrangements. Multiple

project websites and digital resources became inaccessible during or immediately after the High Street HAZ programme period, demonstrating what digital preservation scholars term "digital dark ages" (Conway, 2010).

In Kirkham, the closure of the "Kirkham Treasures" website resulted in the loss of cultural programme outputs that had been accessible only through that platform (available via archived copy captured on 06 Feb 2025:

<https://web.archive.org/web/20250206153722/https://kirkhamtreasures.co.uk/>).

Similarly, the Northallerton Heritage Hub website faced uncertainty beyond its initial five-year domain registration, despite containing significant community-generated heritage content.

The platform precarity was particularly acute for innovative digital outputs such as augmented reality applications and interactive heritage trails (Figure 9). These digital innovations were engaging but fragile, reliant on ongoing maintenance and shifting platform compatibilities. Social media platforms such as the "Kirkham & Wesham Memories of the Past" Facebook group functioned as community archives yet remained vulnerable to corporate policies and platform changes. By contrast, established repositories such as the Archaeology Data Service, Historic England databases, and county archives offered durable preservation infrastructure, but institutional policies often led to poor integration with community content, leaving socially valuable outputs exposed to loss.

Figure 9, Augmented reality heritage trail promotional material from Northallerton Heritage Hub (Northallerton Heritage Hub, n.d.)

Discussion

The High Street Heritage Action Zone programme provides a significant case study for understanding the complexities of heritage data management within a national framework of regeneration and conservation. Designed to revitalise 67 English high streets, the initiative generated diverse datasets ranging from oral histories and creative outputs to technical surveys and planning documents, highlighting the challenges and opportunities inherent in managing heritage data for both immediate use and long-term preservation.

The management and legacy of these datasets is essential to mitigate intergenerational loss, particularly in areas experiencing social change or population mobility where continuity of familial or oral histories can no longer be assumed. The High Street HAZ demonstrates how heritage data drives strategic public investment and unlocks wider economic benefits through heritage-led regeneration. According to the AMION evaluation, non-monetised benefits elevated the initiative's success ratings, increasing the Cultural Strand from Medium to High and the Capital Strand from Acceptable to Medium (AMION, 2025). This reflects the broader societal value

of heritage data in fostering identity, pride, and social cohesion within communities (Gallou, 2022; Dorpalen *et al.*, 2023).

Governance Challenges and Data Management Disparities

Despite this value, the High Street HAZ illustrated significant challenges in heritage data governance. Variability in governance and ownership led to inconsistencies across the initiative. Northallerton excelled in professional data archiving through its partnership with North Yorkshire County Records Office, establishing clear custodianship arrangements and formal deposit agreements. This contrasted sharply with Kirkham's informal community custody arrangements, where valuable wellbeing programme outputs remained vulnerable despite their social significance, and Chester's consultant-controlled datasets which remained fragmented despite superior technical quality.

The research reveals systematic hierarchies in heritage data treatment reflecting professional cultures rather than intrinsic data value. Archaeological investigations achieved systematic preservation through established OASIS workflows, whilst above-ground heritage documentation of comparable significance remained within local planning systems without integration into broader heritage infrastructures. This disparity cannot be attributed to technical differences but reflects how regulatory frameworks create divergent institutional expectations, with archaeological work operating under planning conditions mandating comprehensive archiving whilst above-ground heritage documentation faces only advisory preservation guidance.

The Discovery Gap and Platform Precarity

The research identifies a critical "discovery gap" where technical availability does not translate into practical accessibility. Historic Environment Records, designated as "primary sources of information about the historic environment," were accessed by only 41.67% of survey respondents, whilst local archives achieved 83.33% usage rates. Extensive Historic England research on Chester's medieval Rows received minimal engagement from planning applicants despite covering nationally significant heritage assets, with practitioners instead relying on readily available materials through search engines and social media platforms.

This finding demonstrates that data governance extends beyond creation and preservation to encompass discoverability and user experience. The most technically sophisticated datasets remain effectively invisible if they require specialist knowledge or institutional mediation to access, let alone specialist software. This has profound implications for evidence-based heritage management, as decisions may be based on readily available but limited information rather than comprehensive scholarly resources.

Platform precarity emerged as a systematic threat to digital heritage preservation, with multiple project websites, social media archives, and innovative digital formats becoming inaccessible during or shortly after programme completion. The closure of the "Kirkham Treasures" website and vulnerability of Facebook groups as heritage data repositories demonstrate fundamental mismatches between innovation timescales and preservation requirements, reflecting systematic bias towards outputs demonstrating immediate impact rather than long-term cultural value.

Community Data and Institutional Recognition

Community engagement components generated innovative and socially valuable heritage datasets yet proved most vulnerable to loss through inadequate governance arrangements. Community-generated content often captured intangible heritage absent from formal records but required distinctive governance approaches balancing institutional preservation capacity with community authority over cultural materials. The success of collaborative approaches, exemplified by Northallerton's Heritage Hub partnership, demonstrates potential for inclusive heritage data governance that balances community authority with professional preservation standards.

However, the systematic exclusion of community-generated content from formal preservation pathways, despite cultural value, demonstrates how institutional priorities shape what heritage knowledge receives preservation, supporting arguments that heritage data governance is fundamentally political rather than technical (Gray *et al.*, 2018). The tension between community expectations and institutional limitations highlights the need for transparent governance frameworks that acknowledge resource constraints whilst maximising preservation potential.

Implications for Heritage Data Governance

The findings reveal that governance frameworks, rather than resource constraints or technical limitations, determined long-term accessibility and preservation outcomes.

The multi-stakeholder environment created natural experiments revealing both opportunities and constraints in collaborative heritage practice, extending analysis of heritage data governance beyond traditional museum or research frameworks into planning and regeneration contexts.

The research demonstrates how regeneration contexts create distinctive challenges requiring coordinated institutional responses. Without systematic approaches to data integration, valuable heritage information defaults to institutional priorities rather than public benefit considerations. The absence of mandatory governance frameworks created cascading effects throughout project lifecycles, with heritage data often defaulting to storage within data creators' organisational servers, creating substantial variations in data quality and accessibility.

The study reveals three critical factors determining data governance outcomes:

Institutional Capacity: Sites with dedicated archive partnerships and professional data management expertise achieved superior preservation outcomes regardless of project scale or technical sophistication. The contrast between Northallerton's systematic approach and Kirkham's ad hoc arrangements demonstrates how institutional support transforms data outcomes.

Professional Culture: Archaeological data management success reflects established professional norms and regulatory requirements, whilst above-ground heritage documentation remains subject to individual practitioner discretion. This disparity suggests that professional standards and expectations shape outcomes more than technical capabilities.

Access Mechanisms: The discovery gap between technically available and practically accessible heritage data highlights the critical importance of user experience in determining data utility. Sophisticated datasets remain effectively invisible without appropriate discovery and access mechanisms.

Policy Implications and Recommendations

The research suggests four priority interventions building on existing infrastructure whilst remaining achievable within current institutional constraints:

1. Mandatory Data Management Plans: All publicly funded heritage projects should require DMPs using standardised templates specifying file formats, repository destinations, and licensing arrangements. These should be proportionate to project scale but consistent in covering preservation, access, and intellectual property considerations.

2. Intellectual Property Reform: Clear clauses should ensure publicly funded datasets remain accessible for public benefit, with commercial providers retaining limited rights for specified periods rather than indefinite ownership. This would address the systematic barrier created by current consultancy arrangements.

3. Equivalent Archival Requirements: Above-ground heritage data should be subject to the same systematic archiving requirements as archaeological material, extending OASIS-style workflows to building recording, conservation documentation, and planning-related heritage research.

4. HER Investment: Historic Environment Records require targeted investment to become active governance partners rather than passive recipients, with enhanced discovery interfaces and systematic integration of community-generated content.

These changes would address core governance failures whilst establishing hybrid governance models that balance national consistency with local autonomy, ensuring governance frameworks match heritage data complexity whilst prioritising long-term public access over short-term commercial convenience.

Conclusion

This research demonstrates that heritage data governance within Historic England's High Street HAZ programme reflects broader structural challenges for how cultural information is valued, managed, and preserved in contemporary regeneration contexts. While the programme generated substantial volumes of heritage data across planning, community engagement, and research domains, systematic analysis reveals significant gaps in coordination, preservation, and public access that limit the long-term value of public investment in heritage documentation.

The key findings challenge common assumptions about heritage data governance. Data quality and preservation outcomes reflect governance arrangements and institutional capacity rather than technical constraints alone. Sites with structured partnerships and systematic preservation planning achieved superior outcomes regardless of project scale, while sites with fragmented responsibility experienced significant data loss despite producing technically sophisticated outputs. The analysis exposes systematic hierarchies in heritage data treatment that reflect professional cultures rather than intrinsic data value, with below-ground archaeological investigations receiving systematic archival treatment while above-ground heritage documentation remained fragmented within local planning systems.

The research reveals significant tensions between commercial intellectual property practices and principles of public access to publicly funded research. Standard consultancy arrangements retain data rights with commercial providers despite substantial public investment, creating barriers to integration and reuse. This represents fundamental misalignment between public funding objectives and data governance outcomes that requires coordinated policy intervention.

Data accessibility and discoverability prove critical for promoting reuse. Heritage information in easily accessible repositories was consistently reused across planning, research, and community contexts, while materials requiring specialist access remained largely unused despite potential relevance. This finding suggests that accessibility improvements may yield greater impact than simply increasing data volume.

Community engagement revealed both innovative approaches to participatory heritage documentation and significant vulnerabilities arising from inadequate institutional support. Community-generated content often captured intangible heritage absent from formal records but required active advocacy and institutional partnership for systematic preservation. Platform precarity emerged as a systematic threat, with multiple project websites and digital formats becoming inaccessible during programme completion, highlighting tensions between innovation and sustainability.

The methodological approach, combining interviews, questionnaires, and data audits, proved essential for understanding the complexity of heritage data governance. The interview data provided crucial insights into why certain practices developed and how stakeholders navigated institutional constraints, whilst questionnaire responses revealed systematic patterns across the programme. Data audits provided objective verification of preservation outcomes, revealing gaps between stated intentions and achieved results. This triangulation was particularly important given the sensitive nature of institutional critique within professional networks.

The policy implications extend beyond individual project management to encompass sector-wide governance reform. Future heritage regeneration programmes require mandatory data management planning, clear intellectual property frameworks ensuring public access to publicly funded outputs, and systematic preservation arrangements aligned with established heritage repositories. Professional standards need development to ensure equivalent treatment of different heritage domains, whilst infrastructure investment is required to support both technical and human capacity for heritage data stewardship.

Heritage data governance represents a critical policy domain that has received inadequate attention within both heritage studies and regeneration policy. The systematic fragmentation and preservation failures documented reflect structural gaps in how cultural information is valued and sustained within contemporary governance arrangements. Realising the potential for heritage data to serve multiple stakeholder needs, supporting evidence-based planning, enabling community engagement, facilitating research, and promoting sustainable regeneration, requires coordinated institutional reform that recognises data governance as core to programme effectiveness.

The research demonstrates the importance of viewing heritage data governance through multiple analytical lenses. From a technical perspective, the predominance of PDF formats and reliance on commercial platforms creates systematic barriers to long-term accessibility and computational analysis. From an institutional perspective, the absence of coordinated governance frameworks creates fragmentation and loss

despite individual good intentions. From a political perspective, current arrangements privilege commercial interests over public access, undermining the democratic potential of publicly funded heritage research.

With appropriate institutional support, coordinated standards, and systematic preservation planning, heritage regeneration programmes can generate lasting digital legacies that contribute to cumulative cultural knowledge. However, achieving this potential requires recognising data governance as central to heritage practice with corresponding investment in infrastructure, standards, and institutional capacity. The alternative, continued fragmentation and underutilisation, represents not only poor value for public investment but fundamental failure of cultural stewardship that undermines the long-term goals of heritage-led regeneration.

The High Street HAZ programme demonstrates both the potential and the challenges of heritage data governance in regeneration contexts. While significant datasets were created and some innovative approaches developed, the lack of systematic coordination resulted in substantial loss of cultural information and missed opportunities for broader public benefit. Future programmes must learn from these experiences to ensure that heritage data governance matches the ambition and public investment of heritage-led regeneration initiatives.

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Data and supplementary information availability

The data and supplementary information for this paper is accessible at Zenodo at:

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